

The Role of Economic Planning in fostering India's Socio-Economic Development

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Abstract:

Since India's Independence in 1947 it has made significant economic progress. On an average of the national income over the last decade shows that the real national income has increased at annual rate of about 3%. Productive capacity in the Indian economy has increased through increasing investment and the rate of economic performance has been grown effectively. There is little doubt that the Indian economy is moving away from dead centre and cannot be characterized as "stagnant," a term which could have been applied to it with some justification during the earlier decades.

It is, however, clear that this rate of growth is small relative to the rate of population increase, which has been estimated to be 1.5% per annum. The rate of increase of per capita income, therefore, comes to 1.5% per annum. If the rate of increase of population accelerates in the future, as some experts forecast on very good grounds, the present rate of increase of national income will be completely inadequate and India will have to grow faster even to keep it at the same level of per capita income.

There is considerable evidence, both official and un-official, from Indian and foreign observers, to indicate that the development effort in India during the last decade has been characterized by much inefficiency and waste. The available economic resources have not been as productively used under the given conditions as they could have been and when one begins to consider and analyses this, he soon comes up with the fact that the causes lie deep in the whole Indian cultural and social setup and that it involves the whole problem of the social efficiency of the Indian society. To anticipate. This us first substantiate the opening gambit that the Indian development effort during the fifties which was inefficient.

Perhaps we can begin by the observations of the latest Indian delegation to China, which visited that country early in 1959 to study the Chinese achievements in the conservation and maximum utilization of water, including rain water. What the delegation found most impressive, which was the type of organisation employed for achieving the remarkable results in this field rather than the use of any new techniques which were being used in China and which were not known or used in India.

Objectives:

The guiding principles of Indian planning are provided by the basic objectives of growth, modernization, self-reliance and social Justice. Within this with Framework, each five- year plan involves some directional changes to take into account with new constraints and possibilities. The seventh plan, as stated in the approach paper approved by the National Development Council, seeks to emphasis policies and programmes which will accelerate the growth in food grains

production, increase employment opportunities and raise productivity.

Strategy:

The central element in the development strategy of the Seventh plan is the generation of productive employment. This will be achieved through increase in cropping intensity made possible by increased availability of irrigation facilities, extension of new agricultural technologies to low productivity regions and to

small farmers, through measures to make the rural development programmes more effective in the creation of productive assets, through the expansion of labour intensive construction activities for providing housing, urban amenities, roads and rural infrastructure, and also through the expansion of primary education and basic health facilities and through changes in the pattern of industrial growth. With this emphasis on the generation of productive employment, the Seventh plan aims at a significant reduction in the growth of poverty and improvement in the quality of life for the poor in the villages and towns. There is also a need to generate employment opportunities for educated youth in rural areas. The expansion of education and health facilities will open new job opportunities and the spread of credit Institutions and other developmental activities will create opportunities for self-employment.

Economic planning strategy in India:

In order to achieve the long-term and short-term objectives set in the each five year, specific strategies are required. It involves allocation resources across different sectors of the economy in tandem with the specified objectives. It involves selection choices like development of agriculture sector or industrial sector, public or private sector involvement, closed economy or open economy model. Indian planning strategies can be split into two phases: pre-1991 phase and post-1991 phase.

Pre 1991 Phase or Pre- Reform Phase:

During pre-1991 phase (1951 to 1990), India followed the strategy of planning with greater reliance on the public sector along with a regulated private sector. Following strategies are followed during 1951-91 phase.

Heavy Reliance on Public Sector:

Greater Reliance was placed on public sector compared to private sector. As private sector was not able to invest in large amount for development of heavy industries, government turned towards public sector for provision of essential and basic needs for the people. At the same time private sector was not willing to provide the services in backward regions of the country.

Regulated Expansion of Private Sector:

Private sector was restricted to few areas of activities. New legislations were created for the restriction for the restriction of private sector.

Development of Heavy Industries:

Government invested heavily in development of Heavy industry like iron industry.

Protection of Small Scale Industry:

Small scale industry was protected by means of establishment of boards for different small scale industries and reserving few areas of production exclusively for the small scale industry.

Inward Looking Trade Strategy:

Domestic industry was protected from competition in the international market. Heavy import duty was imposed to curb competitive imports, while domestic Industries were encouraged to produce domestic substitutes of essential imports.

Thrust on Savings and Investment:

Promotion of Savings and investment was the undisputed objective of monetary and fiscal policies of the government. Savings are induced through high rate of interest. Tax concessions were to mobilise savings.

Restriction of Foreign Capital:

Several types of restrictions were imposed on foreign direct investment. To control and regulate it, Foreign Exchange Regulation Act (FERA) was enforced.

Post 1991 phase (Post-reform Phase):

Strategy of planning in India with witnessed a marked shift in the year 1991. Following are main changes observed under NEP (new economic policy):

- Fiscal policy and monetary policy have been reoriented to facilitate the free play of market forces.
- Foreign capital in the form of FDI (foreign direct investment) and FII (Foreign Institutional Investment) are encouraged.
- Import restrictions are restricted to the minimum, while export promotion has been accorded a high priority.
- Competition rather than controls have become the fulcrum of growth process.
- Direct participation of the government is significantly tempered and confined only to strategic industries such as atomic energy, minerals and railways.
- Partial convertibility of Indian Rupee.

Recently, the concept of Sustainable development is included as main feature of the strategy of planning in India. Sustainable development refers to the development of present generation by taking into consideration of the future generations.

Following are some notable reasons for change in economic policy:

1. Mounting Fiscal Deficit and revenue deficit: Fiscal deficit and revenue deficit of the country are increased due to the policies followed before the 1990's governments.
2. Balance of Payments (BoP) Crisis: Heavy dependence on imports resulted in a BoP Crisis.

3. Gulf Crisis: On account of Iraq war in 1990-91, prices of petrol started increasing. Remittances from gulf countries are also stopped.
4. Fall in Foreign Exchange Reserves: In 1990-91, India's foreign exchange reserves lowered to such a level that these were not enough to pay for an import bill of 10 days.
5. Rise in Prices: In India prices happened to rise rapidly. Expansion in money supply was the principal cause of inflationary pressures. In turn, this was relate to deficit financing. It has experienced the situation of stagflation.
6. Dismal Performance of Public Sector Undertakings (PSUs): Public sector undertakings were shown dismal performance.

On account of all these factors, the government shifted to New Economics Policy.

Strategic Pillars of National Strategy for Financial Inclusion:

To achieve the vision of ensuring access to an array of basic formal financial services, a set of guiding objectives have been formulated with special relevance in the Indian context.

1. Universal Access to Financial Services: Every village to have access to a formal financial service provider within a reasonable distance of 5 KM radius. The customers may be on barded through an easy and hassle-free digital process and processes should be geared towards a less paper ecosystem.
2. Providing Basic Bouquet of Financial Services: Every adult who is willing and eligible needs to be provided with a basic bouquet of financial services that include a Basic Savings Bank Deposit Account, credit, a micro life and non-life insurance product, a pension product and a suitable investment product.
3. Access to Livelihood and Skill Development: The new entrant to the financial system, if

eligible and willing to undergo any livelihood / skill development programme, may be given the relevant information about the ongoing Government livelihood programmes thus helping them to augment their skills and engage in meaningful economic activity and improve income generation.

4. Customer Protection and Grievance Redressal: Customers shall be made aware of the resources available for resolution of their grievances. About storing and sharing of customer's biometric and demographic data, adequate safeguards need to be ensured to protect the customer's right to privacy.
5. Effective Co-ordination: There needs to be a focused and continuous coordination between the key stakeholders viz. Government, the Regulators, financial service providers, Telecom Service Regulators, Skills Training institutes etc. to make sure that the customers are able to use the services in a sustained manner. The focus shall be to consolidate gains from previous efforts through focus on improvement of quality of service of last mile delivery viz., capacity building of Business Correspondents, creating payments system for ecosystems at village levels to deepen the culture of digital finance leading to ease to use and delivery.

Conclusion:

An analysis of these causes, however, is not easy. First, our own limitations as a social scientist are overwhelming. Secondly, it involves introspection, a difficult art to practice anywhere. Being a part of the Indian society and having been born and brought up in it, we are not sure of our ability to look at it from outside from a critical angle. We decided, however, to make the effort, perhaps in a foolhardy way, because we thought somebody must begin to do this sometime, and if we are wrong at least it would provoke abler minds to attempt the task sadly neglected so far.

We have to examine for this purpose the social efficiency of the Indian society as a whole in relation to economic and social development. But as Davis observes in the matter of societal efficiency we have a concept but little else. In practice it is hedged about by the preconceptions and institutions of a going society; in social science it is handicapped by the unreality of ignoring these practical limitations and by the lack of and adequate set of measuring devices. The concept says: Given a certain quantum of natural resources two together for the production of goods and services, some of these ways being more effective than others. But it does not tell parts of the social system. We can make use to such makeshift indices as exist, but in the last analysis we are thrown back on speculation and general theory.

To conclude one must think to begin by analyzing the basic ways and the traditional Indian or Hindu society, note the changes that have taken place in them in modern times under British rule, and then try to see if these in principle and in fact give some clues to the analysis of the complex problem.

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